

Supplementary Material for:

Inhibitory effect of lignin on the hydrolysis of xylan by thermophilic and thermolabile GH11 xylanases

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Fig. S1. SDS-PAGE of purified xylanases: TrXyn1 (left gel, lane 5), TrXyn2 (left gel, lane 6), Xyl40 (right gel), Xyl40-CD pool 1(left gel, lane 8) and Xyl40-CD pool 2 (left gel, lane 1). TrXyn1, TrXyn2 and the two pools of Xyl40-CD were run on one gel and Xyl40 on a separate gel. For comparison, the same molecular weight standard (STD) was run on both gels.

Fig S2. SDS-PAGE analysis of deglycosylation of Xyl40-CD.

Lane 1, molecular weight standard. Lane 2, Pool 2 from Xyl40-CD purification. Lane 3, Pool 2 from Xyl40-CD purification after incubation with endoH for 30 min.

Table S1. Composition of the enzymatic hydrolysis residue (EnzHR) lignin isolated from steam pretreated spruce.

	Glucose	Xylose	Mannose	Total polysaccharides	Acid soluble lignin	Acid insoluble lignin	Nitrogen
EnzHR	13.2	0.3	0.4	12.8	0.6	85.0	0.4

Presented as % (w/w) of dry matter.

Table S2. Effect of soluble phenolic compounds on the hydrolysis yields of xylan by xylanases TrXyn1, TrXyn2, Xyl40-CD and Xyl40. Yield are presented as % out of the control sample without a phenol and standard deviation of triplicates is in parenthesis. Hydrolysis was performed in 1 % (w/V) xylan concentration at 40 °C with a phenol concentration of 0, 10, 100 or 1000 mg/ml.

Phenol concentration	TrXyn1			TrXyn2			Xyl40-CD			Xyl40		
	10 (mg/ml)	100 (mg/ml)	1000 (mg/ml)									
acetovanillone	99 (1)	103 (2)	98 (2)	100 (4)	105 (1)	99 (4)	97 (2)	98 (1)	99 (3)	103 (2)	110 (4)	107 (4)
p-coumaric acid	96 (3)	95 (2)	102 (1)	100 (3)	99 (3)	100 (1)	102 (2)	96 (1)	93 (0)	92 (6)	97 (5)	76 (6)
ferulic acid	111 (1)	112 (3)	113 (1)	100 (1)	100 (0)	98 (2)	105 (4)	96 (10)	106 (6)	96 (10)	96 (10)	87 (3)
homovanillyl alcohol	104 (2)	100 (3)	101 (3)	106 (3)	101 (3)	106 (1)	101 (1)	103 (4)	102 (2)	106 (8)	105 (15)	96 (6)
protocatechuic acid	107 (1)	102 (2)	106 (3)	102 (2)	102 (1)	102 (1)	100 (2)	103 (2)	102 (2)	104 (5)	105 (6)	98 (6)
syringaldehyde	98 (5)	87 (2)	50 (4)	102 (1)	100 (2)	94 (3)	101 (1)	100 (4)	91 (5)	105 (8)	102 (4)	83 (11)
syringic acid	101 (1)	109 (2)	103 (5)	97 (1)	102 (3)	101 (1)	93 (5)	98 (2)	95 (3)	104 (3)	109 (4)	96 (4)
vanillic acid	95 (3)	99 (4)	108 (4)	114 (1)	104 (8)	105 (4)	101 (1)	102 (2)	98 (6)	113 (8)	108 (2)	93 (3)
vanillin	85 (4)	90 (5)	102 (9)	101 (1)	102 (1)	102 (3)	104 (2)	102 (1)	101 (3)	109 (11)	110 (6)	122 (2)